

MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES, LEADERSHIP CRISIS PRACTICES AND WORK COMMITMENT IN IMPROVING SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

PRECIOUS JOY P. ARELLANO

preciousjoy.arellano@deped.gov.ph
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2444-8726>
Laguna State Polytechnic University

ABSTRACT

School leaders play a vital role in an educational system. They are accountable for carrying out the mission and objectives of the school. This study investigates the effect of the school head management competencies, leadership crisis practices, and work commitment in improving school performance. It utilized quantitative and descriptive research approaches to gather data. The respondents of this study were 213 public elementary teachers of Candelaria West District. It was conducted during the second quarter of the school year 2020-2021. A researcher-made questionnaire was used in generating data. Based on the finding, the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the performance of the school and that of management competencies, leadership crisis practices, and work commitment of the school head. Based on the above findings, the following recommendations are given: It is suggested that school administrators consider open communication in the workplace since it creates harmonious relationships, which in turn lead to increased productivity and the achievement of school goals. Next is, school leaders may strengthen the use of political frame in their organization to influence others around them, create and broaden their partnerships with stakeholders, and motivate them to support their school's decisions and actions in achieving success. Also, school administrators may intensify their level of work commitment since it motivates teachers and pupils to carry out their responsibilities effectively and efficiently, leading to school improvement. Lastly, a follow-up study can be conducted using a regression analysis to identify the predictors of school performance to the future researcher.

Keywords: Management Competencies, Leadership Crisis Practices, Work Commitment, School Performance